

Comparative job satisfaction of Public & Private sector Bank Employees (ICICI and SBI).

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INTRODUCTION

The banking system plays very important role to develop an economy by enabling it to be competitive and strong enough to face any financial problem and hence forms the core of money market in an advance country. The banking structure of every economy is going to change with the changing environment.

Banks are the most significant players in the Indian financial market because they are the biggest purveyors of credit and attract most of the savings from the population. Banking plays very important role in the economic development of all the nations of the world because developed banking system holds the key as well as serves as a barometer of economic health of a country.

As banking institutions are the backbone of a nation's economy, the well-organized management of human resources and the maintenance of higher job satisfaction levels influence the growth and performance of an entire economy. The Indian banking sector is a fast-growing financial service sector that has seen remarkable progress after nationalization. The Indian banking system can be generally categorized into "scheduled commercial banks" and "non-scheduled commercial banks". Scheduled commercial banks can be further classified into public sector banks, private sector banks. Over time, differences have been observed between public sector banks and private sector banks in terms of various operational and efficiency parameters.

Public sector bank

Government is the holder of major stake (i.e. more than 50%) in these banks. The shares of these banks are listed on stock exchanges. There are a total of 26 PSBs in India. They are dominating the commercial banking system and controlling almost 80% of the businesses in India.

Private sector

All those banks which are not owned by government and where greater stake or equity is held by the private shareholders are known as "private-sector banks". In this type of banks, the majority of share capital is held by private individuals and corporate. All private sector banks were not nationalized in 1969, and 1980. The private banks which were not nationalized are collectively known as the old private sector banks.

SBI

Imperial Bank was nationalized in 1955 with the emergence of Central Govt. in the banking business. RBI held 60% of the total stake and a new bank named State bank of India was emerged. The seven other banks were nationalized on 19th July 1960 and became the subsidiaries of SBI. Another 14 major banks were nationalized in 1969 by the government of India. The total deposits in these nationalized banks amounted to 50 crores. The next level of nationalization took place in April 1980 with the nationalization of six more banks.

The overall deposits of such banks amounted to be around 200 crores.

The State Bank of India (SBI) is the largest Indian bank and financial services company (by turnover and total assets) with its headquarters in Mumbai, India.

ICICI

In 1994, the *Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India* established *ICICI Bank*, to undertake commercial banking operations - taking deposits, credit cards, car loans etc.

ICICI Bank is one of the Big Four banks of India, along with State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank and HDFC Bank—its main competitors.

ICICI Bank Limited is a major banking and financial services company based in Mumbai. It is the second largest bank in India and the largest private sector bank in India by market capitalization. The bank also has a network of branches. ICICI Bank offers a wide range of banking products and financial services to corporate and retail customers through a variety of delivery channels and specialization subsidiaries and affiliates in the areas of investment banking, life and non-life insurance, venture capital and asset management. ICICI Bank is also the largest issuer of credit cards in India.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out overall job satisfaction of public and private sector bank employees.

- To identify the factors which are responsible for satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the bank employees.
- To compare the job satisfaction level of employees of public sector and private sector banks.
- To suggest effective ways of improving job satisfaction among the employees of banking sector.
- To determine whether there is a statistically significant relationship between job satisfaction and work in present job, remuneration, supervision, promotion and co-workers amongst employees in a public & private sector bank.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Wolman and Kruger (2001, p. 11) define a hypothesis as “a tentative assumption or preliminary statement about the relationship between two or more things that needs to be examined.”

There will be a significant relationship between variables (namely, occupational class, race, gender, educational level, tenure, age, marital status, income and job status) and job satisfaction amongst employees in a public & private sector banks.

SAMPLE

The total sample is consisting of 300 employees. Out of them 150 from public sector (SBI) and 150 from private sector bank (ICICI). The employees those we taken as sample is of all the three levels of management i.e. (upper management, middle management and lower management).

Tool for the Study

Job satisfaction scale is framed through Linker method of scaling. The questionnaire using 5-Scale Linker (1 Strongly satisfied, 2 Satisfied, 3 Neutral 4 Strongly dissatisfied 5 Dissatisfied) design to test the impact of all the variables. For this study the questionnaire is divided into 2 sections demographic variables and facets of job satisfaction. The questionnaire cover all the variables such as educational qualifications, nature of work, pay, job security, promotional opportunities and no. of depended & work environment. The data were analyzed through SPSS v.19

REWEIVE

Simultaneously Knights et al (2005) also indicated no difference of job satisfaction ratings on the basis of age, educational level, tenure, and job location among 13 state government departments in Queensland Australia.

According to Sargent and Hannum (2005) that employees characteristics such as age, gender, marital status, level of education and the rank may have positive or negative effect on the job satisfaction. They have reported that younger employees are more dissatisfied than their older counterparts which suggest that the age is an important determinants in the job satisfaction. Newly inducted and most senior employees reported to be very dissatisfied and only those who were in the middle rank stated to be the most satisfied. Employees having less education more satisfaction with their job than those who were qualified.

Metle (2002) states that only work environment development is not enough to enhance job satisfaction level but to take into consideration the inclusion of traditional culture is also necessary. Best et al (2006) identify salary and autonomy as distinguishing job satisfaction predictor among Public sector employees. CHU et al,(2003) proved that autonomy, distributive justice, sample opportunities for promotion and supervisor support may help to enhance level of job satisfaction among employees.

JOB SATISFACTION ANALISIS ON DIFFERENT JOB ASPECT

Job satisfaction is regard to one's feeling or state of mind regarding the nature of their work. Job satisfaction can be influenced by variety of factors such as kind of supervision, organization policies & administration, salary & quality of life etc.

Table: Comparative job Satisfaction according Pay

Pay plays a significant role in determining of satisfaction. Pay is instrumental in fulfilling so many needs. Money facilitates the obtaining of food, shelter, and clothing and provides the means to enjoy valued leisure interest outside of work Over pay can serve as symbol of achievement and source of recognition. Employees often see pay as a reflection of organization. Fringe benefits have not been found to have strong influence on job satisfactions direct wages.

Pay satisfaction has been shown to influence overall job satisfaction, motivation and performance, absenteeism and turnover intensions, and may be related to pay-related Grievances and lawsuits. Pay has been considered an important reward to motivate the behavior of employees.

Determining wages and salaries is one of the most critical aspects of human resources management. It has a significant impact on recruitment,

motivation and satisfaction of the employees. Therefore, designing and structuring of pay system is very crucial

to the effectiveness of organizations.

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank S B I			
		1-2 Lakhs	2-3 Lakhs	3-4 Lakhs	Above 4 Lakhs	1-2 Lakhs	2-3 Lakhs	3-4 Lakhs	Above 4 Lakhs
1	Strongly satisfied	2	5	7	2	4	20	25	2
2	Satisfied	8	10	12	3	5	18	20	3
3	Neutral	3	9	2	1	3	5	3	1
4	Dissatisfy	16	9	5	10	2	9	10	3
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	22	10	7	7	4	4	3	6
Total		51	43	33	23	18	56	61	15

This Table shows the comparative job satisfaction of both bank employees according to pay scale. Majority of private sector bank employees 34% (51) get lower pay scale from 1-2 lakhs only. In public sector bank majority of employees 41% (61) get high scale of pay from 3-4 lakhs.

In private sector maximum of employees 31% (46) strongly dissatisfied and 11% (16) employees strongly satisfied from all pay scale levels

In public sector maximum of employees 34% (51) strongly satisfied and 11% (17) employees strongly dissatisfied from all pay scale levels.

Pay is the powerful factor of job satisfaction. In private sector dissatisfaction level is high due to lower pay from job.

Table: Comparative job Satisfaction according increment

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank S B I			
		Employees	% value	Mean	SD	Employees	% value	Mean	SD
1	Strongly satisfied	15	10	30	19	48	32	30	13
2	Satisfied	22	15			37	25		
3	Neutral	13	9			17	11		
4	Dissatisfy	42	28			28	19		
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	58	39			20	13		
Total		150	101			150	100		

Increment is a system of monetary motivation to employees. Every employee waits their increment very angrily. There is a positive relationship between increment and job satisfaction. The system of increment is different in both sector bank in public sector sector bank it is depend upon mostly on govt. norms and in public sector it is depend upon varies factor for ex. Work load, efficiency, post, experience, relation to manager, targets, achievements and some employees say

that it is depend upon luck also. Increment depends upon inflation rates. Private sector banks also try that their employees satisfied from this.

In Private sector majority of employees 39 % (58) are strongly dissatisfied and 28 % (42) dissatisfied from increments. They explained that increment system is not equal as inflation rates. It is very low that life cannot survive. In public sector Majority of employees 32% (48) strongly satisfied and 25 % (37) satisfied from increment policy.

Satisfaction level is higher in public sector bank in reference of increment.

Table: Comparative job satisfaction according perks

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank SBI			
		Employees	% value	Mean	SD	Employees	% value	Mean	SD
1	Strongly satisfied	24	16	30	12.47	58	38	30	20.85
2	Satisfied	29	19			45	30		
3	Neutral	13	9			7	5		
4	Dissatisfy	40	27			21	14		
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	44	29			19	13		
		150	100			150	100		

This table shows the comparative job satisfaction according perks facilities given by banks. In both banks different types of perks given by banks. In private sector majority of employees 29 % (44) strongly dissatisfied, 27 % dissatisfied, 19% satisfied and only 16% strongly satisfied. This shows that private sector provide lower perks. In public sector majority 38 % (58) strongly satisfied, 30 % (45) satisfied, 14% (21) dissatisfied and only 13% strongly dissatisfied. This shows that public sector provide higher perks.

Table: Comparative job satisfaction according promotion

A better opportunity for promotion too is a factor, which lead to higher job satisfaction promotion indicates on employee's works to the organization which highly moderate boosting. Employees take promotion is the ultimate achievement in his career and when it is realized he feels extremely satisfied. It is true that individual seek satisfaction in their job in the context of job nature and work environment but they also attach importance to the opportunity for promotion that these job offer

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank SBI			
		Employees	% value	Mean	SD	Employees	% value	Mean	SD
1	Strongly satisfied	22	14	30	27	44	29	30	
2	Satisfied	25	17			39	26		
3	Neutral	11	7			15	10		
4	Dissatisfy	43	29			30	20		
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	50	33			22	15		
		150	100			150	100		

This table shows the comparatively job satisfaction of both sectors bank employees according to promotion. Promotion is a way of non monetary motivation there is a positive relationship between promotion and job satisfaction. In public sector bank promotion is depend upon fixed rules and regulation whereas in private sectors promotion is totally depend upon manager.

Majority of employees 33% (50) strongly dissatisfied, 29% (43) dissatisfied only 14% (22) strongly satisfied and 17% (25) satisfied from promotion.

In public sector bank 29% (44) strongly satisfied, 26 % (39) satisfied, 20% (30) dissatisfied and 15% (22) strongly dissatisfied from promotion system.

Table: Comparative job Satisfaction according Leave facility

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI						Public Sector Bank SBI					
		ML	%	PL	%	CL	%	ML	%	PL	%	CL	%
1	Strongly satisfied	14	10	10	7	29	19	40	27	35	23	20	13
2	Satisfied	23	15	4	3	32	21	38	25	30	20	17	11
3	Neutral	20	13	3	2	15	10	14	9	20	13	25	17
4	Dissatisfy	38	25	53	35	30	20	25	17	36	24	40	27
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	55	37	80	53	44	29	33	22	29	19	48	32
Total		150	100	150	100	150	100	150	100	150	100	150	100

There are three types of leave facilities given by bank. The employees want a break after long time work and a lot of emergencies also create a circumstance of leave. Leave is also a right of employees if it is according to norms so it a power full factor on which employee’s satisfaction is depends. The norms of leave are differ in both sector,

From ICICI maximum employees are strongly dissatisfied and dissatisfied from all type of leave facilities and from SBI maximum employees are strongly dissatisfied and dissatisfied from C.L only In private sector bank all leave facilities not provide to each employee leave provide according post and experience. Higher post and long time than all type of leave provide new comers and lower post than only C. L. provide by bank. In public sector bank all type of leave facilities provide to each employee but they want more than provide so here also lower dissatisfaction level available due to C. L.

Table: Comparative job Satisfaction according working hour

Working hour for bank employees in most of the bank is 0930 to 1800 hrs (08: 30 am to 06:00 PM) but official working hour is 10 Am to 5 PM. As bank manager is responsible for all management so he has to give at least one hour daily more

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank SBI			
		6-8 hours	%	More than 8 hr	%	6-8 hours	%	More than 8 hr	%
1	Strongly satisfied	8	35	13	10	45	36	10	40
2	Satisfied	5	22	19	15	40	32	7	28
3	Neutral	2	9	17	13	25	20	6	24
4	Dissatisfy	4	17	35	28	10	8	1	4
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	4	17	43	34	5	4	1	4
Total		23		127		125		25	

This table shows the satisfaction level of bank employees according to the working hours. Employee’s job satisfaction also affected from working hours as long as working hours employees get lower job satisfaction. In I.C.I.C.I.

maximum employees working hours are more than 8 hours only high post or managers working hours are 8-6 hours. In S.B.I. working hours are fixed according to norms of government only lower post employees and at peak time employees stay more than 8 hours.

Private sectors employees are not satisfied from working hours of bank because every day they do not know the time of their returning at home. Maximum working day the time is not fixed.

Maximum 34% (43) employees are strongly dissatisfied and 28% (35) employees are dissatisfied from working hours .In S.B.I. 36% (45) employees are strongly satisfied in 6-8 hr and 40% (10) are strongly satisfied from more than 8 hr.

Table: Comparative job Satisfaction according other facilities on work place

A motivating environment is one that gives workers a sense of pride in what they do I've created a five-step process called the PRIDE system. e executives and business owners how to accelerate performance and become a top place to work.

- P-Provide a positive working environment
- R-Reward and recognition
- I-Involve and increase employee engagement
- D-Develop the skills and potential of your workforce
- E-Evaluate and make continuous improvements

We can see the working environment different in various bank different. Most of the banks have air condition building, there is separate cabin for each employees and bank manager will also get peon. Overall we can say working environment is good in mostly private sector bank except few bank having over load of work.

S. No.	Satisfaction Level	Private Sector Bank ICICI				Public Sector Bank S B I			
		A/C	Water	Computer	Electricity	A/C	Water	Computer	Electricity
1	Strongly satisfied	65	50	40	60	30	35	25	30
2	Satisfied	30	38	35	40	25	40	30	20
3	Neutral	10	13	20	15	20	15	10	15
4	Dissatisfy	29	30	30	25	40	25	35	35
5	Strongly Dissatisfied	16	19	25	10	35	35	50	50
Total		150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150

Every employee needs some facilities on work place so work going on easy and at rapid rate. Bank job create the requirement of some facilities. In present scenario bank functions are not perfectly handle without the help of computer so it is an essential required in this field and computers are not operate without the supply of proper electricity facility.

In I.C.I.C.I. a large scale of employees are strongly satisfied and satisfied from these facilities. In S.B.I. maximum employees are strongly dissatisfied and dissatisfied from these facilities. In Working environment we can see in various bank different. Most of the banks have air condition building, there is separate cabin for each employees and bank manager will also get peon. Overall we can say working environment is good in mostly private sector bank except few bank having over load of work.

In public sector bank A/C and filter water facilities are not available and computers are not in proper running condition inverters are not available in each branch. These all facilities are available in proper way and in proper amount so Private sector bank employees are highly satisfied from these all facilities.

Suggestions

To overcome this obstacle private sector banks need to introduce Special schemes related retirement, pension, gratuity and other benefits to enhance the employee’s Sense regarding job security in effort to increase organizational commitment which in turn will lead to Employee’s commitment and high degree of satisfaction.

As employees are prime assets for an organization. So, to make loyal employees organization should pay attention to introduce managed operations, provide

incentives and rewards to motivate employees, make job secure and also provide recreational activities to overcome.

The working environment of banks need to be made more cordial and Friendly. Managers are expected to play an active role in the development and grooming of banks and the employees in a friendlier manner. This will reduce the unwanted stress levels of employees.

Both sector banks should give sufficient scope for carrier growth and personnel development of its employees.

The work of employees should be made more pleasant by enriching the job and removing the monotony.

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